

BACKGROUND

There is a 1:4 ratio of female autism patients to male autism patients. Many different hypotheses have been made to potentially explain why this disparity exists.

RESEARCH Q

What features in a given patient contribute to the disparity in autism diagnosis between females and males?

- HYPOTHESIS: Since A7, A10, A11, and A22 assess social interaction skills, female patients with autism are likely to score higher on these measures, making them particularly important features.
 - A7 measures a patient's adherence to standard expectations of social etiquette.
 - A10 measures a patient's ability to maintain focus in a conversation.
 - A11 measures how easy a patient finds social interaction to be.
 - A27 measures how well a patient can pick up on subtext in a conversation.

Note: A7, A10, A11, and A22 above correspond to the scores for Questions #7, #10, #11, and #22 in the dataset "University of California at Irvine (UCI) repository" (for details about this dataset, please refer to the [BASIC SETUP](#) section below).

GOAL

Use a model as described in [BASIC SETUP](#) to check if features contributing to diagnosis outcome are different between male and female dataset.

- End goal is checking for feature importance

BASIC SETUP

1. Dataset being used: University of California at Irvine (UCI) repository for adults, adolescents, and children (age subgroups have the same number of samples).
 - **Target variable: diagnostic yes/no result**

DATASET BREAKDOWN:

- Includes how each participant scored on the Autism Spectrum Quotient (AQ)
 - A1 corresponds to the score (1-4) for Question #1
 - A2 corresponds to the score (1-4) for Question #2
 - Etc.
- Children:

	A1_Score	A2_Score	A3_Score	A4_Score	A5_Score	A6_Score	A7_Score	A8_Score	A9_Score	A10_Score	...	gender	ethnicity	jundice	austim	contry_of_res	used_app_before	result	age_desc	relation	Class/ASD
0	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	...	b'm'	b'Others'	b'no'	b'no'	b'Jordan'	b'no'	5.0	b'4-11 years'	b'Parent'	b'NO'
1	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	...	b'm'	b'Middle Eastern'	b'no'	b'no'	b'Jordan'	b'no'	5.0	b'4-11 years'	b'Parent'	b'NO'
2	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	...	b'm'	b'?	b'no'	b'no'	b'Jordan'	b'yes'	5.0	b'4-11 years'	b'?	b'NO'
3	b'0'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	...	b'f'	b'?	b'yes'	b'no'	b'Jordan'	b'no'	4.0	b'4-11 years'	b'?	b'NO'
4	b'1'	...	b'm'	b'Others'	b'yes'	b'no'	b'United States'	b'no'	10.0	b'4-11 years'	b'Parent'	b'YES'									

- Adolescent:

	A1_Score	A2_Score	A3_Score	A4_Score	A5_Score	A6_Score	A7_Score	A8_Score	A9_Score	A10_Score	...	gender	ethnicity	jundice	austim	contry_of_res	used_app_before	result	age_desc	relation	Class/ASD
0	b'0'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	...	b'm'	b'Hispanic'	b'yes'	b'yes'	b'Austria'	b'no'	6.0	b'12-16 years'	b'Parent'	b'NO'
1	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	...	b'm'	b'Black'	b'no'	b'no'	b'Austria'	b'no'	2.0	b'12-16 years'	b'Relative'	b'NO'							
2	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	...	b'f'	b'?	b'no'	b'no'	b'AmericanSamoa'	b'no'	2.0	b'12-16 years'	b'?	b'NO'							
3	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	...	b'f'	b'White-European'	b'no'	b'no'	b'United Kingdom'	b'no'	7.0	b'12-16 years'	b'Self'	b'YES'
4	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'0'	...	b'f'	b'?	b'no'	b'no'	b'Albania'	b'no'	7.0	b'12-16 years'	b'?	b'YES'						

5 rows x 21 columns

- Adult:

A1_Score	A2_Score	A3_Score	A4_Score	A5_Score	A6_Score	A7_Score	A8_Score	A9_Score	A10_Score	...	gender	ethnicity	jundice	austim	contry_of_res	used_app_before	result	sgc_desc	relation	Class/ASD
0	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	...	b'1'	b'White-European'	b'no'	b'no'	b'United States'	b'no'	6.0	b'18 and more'	b'Self'	b'NO'
1	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	...	b'm'	b'Latino'	b'no'	b'yes'	b'Brazil'	b'no'	5.0	b'18 and more'	b'Self'	b'NO'
2	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'1'	...	b'm'	b'Latino'	b'yes'	b'yes'	b'Spain'	b'no'	8.0	b'18 and more'	b'Parent'	b'YES'
3	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'1'	b'0'	...	b'1'	b'White-European'	b'no'	b'yes'	b'United States'	b'no'	6.0	b'18 and more'	b'Self'	b'NO'
4	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	b'0'	b'0'	b'0'	b'1'	b'0'	b'0'	...	b'1'	b'?	b'no'	b'no'	b'Egypt'	b'no'	2.0	b'18 and more'	b'?	b'NO'

2. Using XGBoost & feature importance with UCI dataset, build two separate models for males and females.
 - a. **UPDATE: Build a single model, later use SHAP to selectively analyze male/female differences**
3. Examine which variables contribute most significantly to the diagnosis outcome, find if there are any differences between males and females.
 - a. Use Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP; **Tree SHAP, implement with XGBoost**) value distributions for more precision
 - If females' SHAP values show that features that emphasize social interaction are more dominant than in males, this could suggest that diagnosis disparity is caused by autistic females being more socially adept than males are and being diagnostically overlooked as a result.
4. **UPDATE: Separate out into train/val/test dataset prior to performing hyperparameter tuning**
5. Perform hyperparameter tuning identically on both models (tune them separately but with the same search procedure).
6. Compare results & evaluation metrics between both models.
 - a. ~~Adjust model(s) by balancing fairness metrics (equalized odds)~~

DIAGRAM

